

STRUCTURE AND CONTENT OF PREPARATION OF THE STUDENT MINI-FOOTBALL TEAM IN THE ANNUAL CYCLE OF CLASSES

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Abstract. Modern professional education is aimed at training specialists who combine versatile education with good health, special professional readiness with a high level of culture, mental and physical performance with a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords: physical performance, physical education, physical culture and sports, mini-football-to universities, strength, agility, endurance.

СТРУКТУРА И СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ МИНИ-ФУТБОЛЬНОЙ КОМАНДЫ В ГОДОВОМ ЦИКЛЕ ЗАНЯТИЙ.

Аннотация. Современное профессиональное образование направлено на подготовку специалистов, которые сочетают разностороннее образование с хорошим здоровьем, специальную профессиональную подготовку с высоким уровнем культуры, умственные и физические способности со здоровым образом жизни.

Ключевые слова: физические способности, физическое воспитание, физическая культура и спорт, мини-футбол в университетах, сила, ловкость, выносливость.

TALABALAR MINI-FUTBOL JAMOASINI YILLIK MASHG'ULOTLAR TSIKLIDA TAYYORLASH TARKIBI VA MAZMUNI

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy kasbiy ta'lim ko'p qirrali ta'limni yaxshi sog'liq, yuqori darajadagi madaniyat bilan maxsus kasbiy tayyorgarlik, aqliy va jismoniy ko'rsatkichlarni sog'lom turmush tarzi bilan birlashtirgan mutaxassislarni tayyorlashga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy ishlash, jismoniy tarbiya, jismoniy tarbiya va sport, mini-futbol-universitetlarga, kuch, chaqqonlik, chidamlilik.

Relevance. According to the results of many studies, one of the main factors for ensuring such a combination is physical education and sports. When discussing the prospects for further development of professional education, many specialists pay attention to the weakened health of modern students, their low motor activity, weak results in terms of motor and physical fitness, and a reduced level of motivation for systematic physical exercises. All these facts taken together characterize the current situation as a crisis, which has a negative impact on the systematic solution of the tasks set in the field of vocational education. It is also emphasized that overcoming this situation is no longer possible due to local adjustment of physical education methods, and in this regard, the need for radical measures to modernize it is postulated.

According to a number of scientists, in order to effectively use the values of physical culture and sports in order to overcome a crisis situation, it is necessary to provide a variety of forms and variability of the content of physical education, which allow organizing the student's motor activity in accordance with his value orientations, interests, and needs. Mini-football classes within the framework of the all-Uzbek project "Mini-football - to universities" are recommended as optimal means of health-improving and conditioning training that can have a complex effect on the body of students, in particular on their functional state and mental sphereuzbek.

The attractiveness of this sport is characterized by many circumstances, among which experts distinguish a variety of examples of games with the appearance of countless combinations, wide opportunities for martial arts with the manifestation of strength, dexterity, endurance.

As a serious positive factor, intensive training of athletes is noted, aimed at developing their resourcefulness, independent creativity, and the implementation of their own ideas in the interests of the entire team.

It should be noted that scientific research on mini-football, before the publication of the project, was more concerned with aspects of designing sports and training programs and methods of training highly qualified players. They almost did not touch upon the possibility of using this game as a basic means of physical education of students, as well as including it in their life activities for sports improvement, active recreation and leisure. Therefore, there are still little-studied questions about the versatile influence of mini-football on the motor and psychophysical development of students, the formation of their motivation, interest and attitudes to systematically engage in this game.

In the context of students' development of the game of mini-football, an important place is occupied by the organization of players of temporary and permanent teams from different degrees and levels of readiness as a form of social development of players of these teams, as well as scientific justification for the preparation of a student team in a one-year cycle of classes.

The subject of the research is the structure and content of the educational and training process of the student mini-football team as the basis for its implementation in the annual cycle of physical education classes.

The aim of the study is to provide a scientific justification of the structure and content of the educational and training process of the student mini-football team in the annual cycle of physical education classes.

In accordance with the purpose, object and subject of the study, the following tasks were set and solved:

1. To study the features of physical development, functional and motor fitness of university students engaged in classical football and mini-football.
2. To identify informative factors for conducting sports orientation of students for mini-football classes.
3. To develop the structure and content of training of the student mini-football team in the annual cycle of classes, which unites students of different levels of health, physical and technical fitness, and to test its effectiveness experimentally.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was the theory of personality and activity, in particular, the provisions on the integrity of human social and biological functions:

- during the development and implementation of program-normative material on the section "Training tools, methods and main sections";
- in the professional and pedagogical activity of teachers of the Department of Physical Education of the university for organizing and conducting mini-football training sessions with students;
- at courses and seminars of retraining and advanced training of teachers of physical education departments, mini-football coaches.

The reliability and validity of the research results is ensured by the theoretical and methodological validity of its initial data, which allows implementing a scientific approach to the study of the problem and proving the hypothesis put forward; the use of modern research methods that are adequate to the goal, subject and tasks; the representativeness of the sample of test subjects, as well as the duration of experimental testing of the effectiveness of training a student's mini-football team in a one-year cycle of classes on physical education.

In episodes.

1. The problem of organizing and training student mini-football teams is not sufficiently developed. The information accumulated in the field of classical football and in the training of professional mini-football players has little to do with the practice of university education.

Data on the state of health, features of motor and physical fitness of students who prefer in-depth mini-football classes are not systematized and are not implemented in the proven technologies of initial selection and sports training. The lack of scientific and methodological provisions and recommendations actualizes the need to develop, justify and implement the structure of training a student's mini-football team in the annual cycle of professional training.

2. Informative indicators that characterize the success of mastering the content and intensity of competitive activity in mini-football are identified. The integral scale for determining students' prospects for mini-football includes the following sections and components: physical fitness (running 30m, running "herringbone", jumping rope in 30 seconds, shuttle run 3x10 m); technical (running the ball on 5x30 m, running the ball 30 m, juggling); functional indicators (level of functional development). conditions, time to reach half of the maximum effort, speed of relaxation of the hip extensor muscles); morphological features (weight-weight index); game activity (expert assessment).

3. The obtained materials allow us to expand the theoretical and practical base of sports training with provisions on structuring the educational and training process and selecting the means of training types based on systematization of data from the informative scale of prospects for beginners and qualified students-mini-football players, to specify individually differentiated parameters of training loads.

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